

Why Open Large Language Models Matter in Rheumatology Research: a Scoping Review

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Abstract (261 words)

Objectives:

To systematically identify and characterize original rheumatology research using large language models (LLMs), quantify reliance on closed versus open models, and assess reporting practices relevant to reproducibility (model versions, prompts, inference settings, and availability of code/data), in order to propose practical recommendations to strengthen transparency.

Methods:

We searched PubMed/MEDLINE for English-language peer-reviewed original research published from 1 November 2022 to 23 January 2026. Two reviewers independently screened title/abstract and full texts, with a third resolving disagreements. Data were extracted using an LLM-assisted workflow and then independently verified against source articles by the authors. Extracted items included study characteristics, model families and openness, access mode, versioning/timing, and transparency indicators (prompts, code, data).

Results:

Of 185 screened records, 63 studies were included. Most were research (n = 26/63; 41.27%) or education-focused (n = 20/63; 31.75%). Studies predominantly used closed-source LLMs (n = 50/63; 79.37%), with limited exclusive use of open-weight models (n = 4/63; 6.35%) and some hybrid use (n = 9/63; 14.29%). OpenAI models were most common (n = 55/63; 87.30%). Reporting was heterogeneous: interaction language was often not reported (n = 42/63; 66.67%); access mode was reported in (n = 19/63; 30.16%); output generation date in (n = 33/63; 52.38%). Prompts were shared in (n = 48/63; 76.19%), but code was publicly available in (n = 4/63; 6.35%), and data in (n = 13/63; 20.63%).

Conclusions:

LLM-based rheumatology research largely depends on closed models with inconsistent reporting of reproducibility-critical details and minimal code sharing. A concise,

rheumatology-oriented checklist is proposed to standardize reporting and improve auditability, replication, and cross-study comparability.

Keywords:

Large language models, Rheumatology, Reproducibility, Open models

Key messages:

What is already known on this topic

- Large language models (LLMs) are increasingly used in biomedical research and rheumatology

What this study adds

- This study provides the first systematic mapping of open versus closed LLM use in rheumatology research
- We found that most of published rheumatology studies using LLMs relied exclusively on closed-source models, and reporting of reproducibility-critical details was heterogeneous.
- We propose a practical rheumatology-oriented reporting checklist to support transparency, reproducibility, and cross-study comparability.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

- Our findings highlight a risk to reproducibility from widespread reliance on closed models.
- The checklist may help authors, reviewers, and editors standardize reporting expectations and facilitate replication and auditability.
- Journal and funder policies could use these minimum reporting items to promote more robust and auditable AI-assisted rheumatology research, whether models are open or proprietary.

Introduction

Reproducibility is fundamental to scientific integrity in rheumatology research, providing the essential basis for independent verification and reliability. Over the past decade, concerns have emerged across multiple scientific disciplines about a reproducibility crisis, prompting calls for greater transparency in methods, data, and analytical workflows [1]. The rapid adoption of large language models (LLMs) has introduced new methodological challenges, particularly regarding transparency, auditability, and replicability [2]. In rheumatology, LLMs are increasingly being used for language-based clinical and research tasks. For example, LLMs have been used for question-answering [3], decision support [4,5], or data extraction [6] across different rheumatology diseases. Because rheumatic diseases are chronic, heterogeneous, and assessed through composite measures and longitudinal narrative notes, small changes in extraction or summarization can propagate into clinically meaningful differences in reported outcomes.

Most LLM-based studies rely on proprietary, closed models whose architectures, training data, and versioning are opaque and subject to change over time. This creates a moving target for replication: the same prompt issued weeks later may be processed by a silently updated model producing systematically different outputs even when the research workflow appears unchanged [7]. Where results cannot be reproduced, LLM-based studies risk offering a snapshot of contemporaneous capabilities rather than enduring, verifiable contributions to cumulative medical science [8]. As a result, the ability to reproduce, validate, or critically assess findings derived from these models is inherently limited, raising important concerns about the scientific robustness of LLM-based research in rheumatology. Moreover, closed-model dependency can create vendor lock-in price increases, shifting access terms, or company failure could strand researchers in costly or unavailable tools.

By contrast, open-source LLMs can be downloaded, modified, and executed locally, enabling researchers to preserve model snapshots and re-run analyses under controlled conditions. Beyond reproducibility, open models have demonstrated promising performance across a range of medical applications [9,10]. However, it remains unclear how open LLMs are being applied in rheumatology, which model types dominate current practice, and whether

published studies report sufficient technical detail to enable replication and meaningful cross-study comparisons.

Objectives

Given this background, this study aimed to systematically identify and characterize original research using LLMs in rheumatology. To do this, a search from 1 November 2022 to 23 January 2026 was conducted. We sought to (i) describe the models used in rheumatology and quantify the extent to which studies rely on closed versus open-source systems, and (ii) evaluate reporting and reproducibility practices, including documentation of model versions, prompts, inference settings when applicable, and code/data availability. Additionally, (iii) we aimed to synthesize common reporting gaps and propose practical recommendations to strengthen transparency and reproducibility in LLM-based rheumatology research.

Materials and methods

Search strategy, study selection, and data charting

We searched PubMed/MEDLINE for peer-reviewed original research on the use of LLMs in rheumatology. The search combined rheumatology terms (MeSH and title/abstract keywords) with LLM-related terms (e.g., “large language model*”, “generative AI”, ChatGPT, GPT-3/4, Claude, Gemini, Bard, Llama, Mistral, chatbot*, “conversational agent*”), and was limited to English-language articles published between 1 November 2022 and 23 January 2026. To reduce irrelevant records at the search stage, we removed reviews (including systematic/scoping/narrative reviews), meta-analyses, editorials, errata, and animal-only studies. We did not exclude correspondence/letters, study protocols/registered reports, viewpoints/comments at the search stage, because some may contain relevant methodological details; instead, these records were assessed during screening and excluded when they did not meet the inclusion criteria. For transparency, we also ran a broader version of the query without these exclusions and quantified records removed by automated filtering as the difference between the broad and final queries. Records were exported and screened in two stages: title/abstract screening followed by full-text review when eligibility was unclear. Two authors (AMG, DB) independently performed both screening stages. A third author (DF) resolved disagreements.

Exclusion criteria

We excluded publications without sufficient methodological detail to confirm the use of an LLM (e.g., generic references to “AI” without specifying an LLM-based approach), including non-LLM chatbot systems (e.g., rule-based or retrieval-only chatbots) and encoder-only NLP models (e.g., BERT-based classifiers). We also did not consider incidental use of LLMs solely for manuscript writing/editing or for code generation (e.g., analysis scripts) when the LLM was not itself evaluated or used to perform a rheumatology task/dataset in the study.

We excluded study protocols/registered reports, guidelines, article replies and reviews misclassified as original research. Correspondence articles/comments/opinions that did not report original results (e.g., no primary evaluation of an LLM in a rheumatology task or dataset) were also removed.

Misclassified animal studies were also excluded.

We further excluded studies where rheumatology was not a substantive component of the objective or dataset, as well as studies focused exclusively on mechanical/degenerative conditions (e.g., low back pain, osteoarthritis, fibromyalgia, osteoporosis, and carpal tunnel syndrome).

The full query can be found in the **Supplementary text “Search query”**.

Data extraction

For each included study, we extracted the predefined variables described in **Supplementary table 1** from the main text and available supplementary materials. We used an LLM-assisted extraction workflow: on 23 January 2026, we downloaded the articles, parsed them using LlamaIndex to generate a machine-readable Markdown input for extraction. We then queried ChatGPT 5.2 (OpenAI) via the application programming interface (API) using a standardized extraction prompt written in English. To minimize context carryover and ensure consistency, each article was submitted to the API as an independent stateless request. We used ChatGPT due to limited computational infrastructure and operational burden associated with deploying and maintaining open-weight models for this workflow.

All LLM-extracted fields were then independently verified by the authors against the source articles (and supplementary materials when applicable), and discrepancies were corrected.. This verification step was undertaken to ensure accuracy, while the LLM-assisted workflow was used primarily to accelerate data extraction.

The full prompt template and the code used for extraction is provided in the **Supplementary material “code”**.

Definitions

LLMs are commonly classified into two categories:

- Closed/proprietary LLMs are systems accessed via hosted interfaces or APIs; their weights and training data are not released, limiting independent auditing and exact reproducibility, and outputs may change as providers update models. Examples of these models are: ChatGPT 5.2, Claude Sonnet 4.5 or Gemini 3 Pro.

- Open models are frequently treated as a single group, but they span two levels of openness:
 - Open-weight LLMs provide downloadable model parameters, enabling local inference and fine-tuning. However, training data, parts of the development pipeline, and/or usage rights may remain restricted by licensing. Examples of these models are Llama 4, Mistral Large 3.
 - Fully open LLMs provide not only weights but also the code and documentation needed to run and, where feasible, reproduce training and evaluation, including clearer reporting of data provenance and training procedures. Examples of these models are BLOOM [11], Pythia [12]

In this work, we use “open” as an umbrella term encompassing both open-weight and fully open models, primarily because fully open LLMs are not yet widely adopted in biomedical/rheumatology research. Examples of widely used open-source LLMs, such as LLaMA, Qwen, or DeepSeek are listed in the **Supplementary table 2**. Several studies have examined the key differences between open LLMs and closed models [7,8,13–15]. **Supplementary table 3** summarizes these differences.

Results

Study selection

We initially identified 201 records. After automated filtering 185 records were assessed for eligibility. A total of 63 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis (Figure 1). The most common reasons for exclusion were lack of substantive rheumatology scope (n = 74/122; 60.66%) and not an eligible LLM application (n = 27/122; 22.13%).

Characteristics of the included articles

Most publications were classified as original articles (n = 53/63; 84.13%), while a smaller proportion were letters, comments or viewpoints reporting original results (n = 10/63; 15.87%). Figure **2A**.

First-author affiliations spanned 18 countries. The most represented countries were China (n = 15/63; 23.81%), Turkey (n = 14/63; 22.22%) and USA (n = 10/63; 15.87%). Figure **2B**.

Rheumatology scope

Across studies, the rheumatology domain was heterogeneous. Most of the studies addressed multiple diseases (n = 28/63; 44.44%). The remaining studies focused on inflammatory autoimmune diseases (n = 21/63; 33.33%), spondyloarthritis (n = 11/63; 17.46%), or other conditions (n = 3/63; 4.76%). Figure 2C.

Study context

Most studies were conducted in research (n = 26/63; 41.27%) and education settings (n = 20/63, 31.75%). The remaining studies were conducted in clinical or mixed settings. Figure 2D.

LLM interaction: language of prompts/inputs

In most of the studies, the language used to interact with the model was not explicitly reported (n = 42/63; 66.67%). From the studies in which the language was reported or could be inferred, English was the predominant interaction language (n = 43/63; 68.25%), together with Chinese (n = 6/63; 9.52%).

Models used, number of models per study, and openness

Most studies evaluated or used a single LLM (n = 35/63; 55.56%). Seven studies (n = 7/63; 11.11%) used two models, and twenty-one (n = 21; 33.33%) used three or more. The maximum number of models used in any study was seven. The most frequently reported model families were OpenAI (n = 55/63; 87.30%), followed by Google (n = 14/63; 22.22%) and Anthropic (n = 10/63; 15.87%). ChatGPT 4 was the model more frequently used (n = 27/63; 42.86%) followed by ChatGPT 4o (n=14/63; 22.22%).

Overall, (n =50/63; 79.36%) of included studies relied exclusively on closed-source LLMs, n = 4/63; 6.35%) used open-weight models, and (n = 9; 14.29%) adopted a hybrid approach combining open and closed systems.

Among studies using open-weight LLMs, the most frequently reported model families were DeepSeek (n = 7/13, 53.84%), Llama (n = 5/13, 38.46%), followed by Qwen and Mistral models (n = 2/13, 15.38%) Several Llama variants were used, including Llama-2, Llama-3, and Llama-

3.1/3.2, while Mistral-7B, Mistral Large, and BioMistral models represented the Mistral ecosystem. Qwen-2.5 models of different parameter sizes and multiple DeepSeek versions (i.e., R1 and V3) were also reported. Less commonly used open models included domain-specific or regional systems such as HuatuoGPT-O1 and Kimi k1.5. Figure 2E.

Access mode and execution details

The access mode to the LLM was explicitly reported in (n = 19/63; 30.16%). Overall, most studies accessed LLMs via a chat-based user interface (n = 49/63; 77.78%), whereas programmatic access (i.e., sending prompts from code, typically via an API, rather than manually using a chat UI), and/or local deployment was less common (n = 10/63; 15.87%). In the remaining studies, access mode was not stated or involved a hybrid approach combining interface-based and programmatic workflows. Among the 11 studies using a programmatic/hybrid access strategy, (n = 7/11; 63.64%) reported at least one model parameter. Figure 2H.

Among studies using chat-based user interfaces, (n = 26/49; 53.06%) explicitly reported measures to control conversational context (e.g., starting a new session or resetting the conversation between cases).

Timing, versioning, and output-generation date

The output generation date (or date of model access) was reported in (n = 33/63; 52.38%)

Transparency: prompts, code, and data availability

Prompts were shared in (n = 48/63; 76.19%) studies. Moreover, across all included studies, code was publicly available in (n = 4/63; 6.25%), while in (n = 59/63; 93.65%) it was not publicly available (including cases where code was not shared, not reported, or not applicable). Data were publicly available in (n = 13/63; 26.56%) studies, available on request in (n = 34/63; 53.97%) and either not publicly available or not applicable in (n = 16/63; 25.49%).

Mentions of openness and reproducibility concerns

Only (n=8/63; 12.70%) of the studies explicitly mentioned the distinction between open and closed models. Figure 2G.

The results table can be found in the **Supplementary spreadsheet “Results table”**.

Checklist

Across included studies, reporting of key technical details (e.g., model versioning, prompts, and inference settings) was heterogeneous, limiting reproducibility and cross-study comparability. To support transparent reporting in rheumatology-specific LLM research, we propose a concise checklist of minimum items that are frequently needed to interpret, replicate, and audit LLM-based methods. This checklist, **Table 1**, is intended to complement, not replace, broader AI reporting frameworks for LLMs [16], such as TRIPOD-LLM [17].

In addition to the items listed in **Table 1**, comprehensive reporting of LLM-based studies should also include detailed descriptions of prompting and interaction strategies (including prompt content, prompting approach, and public availability of prompts), model configuration and inference parameters (e.g., temperature, top-p), and statements on code and data availability, as these elements are essential for full transparency and critical appraisal.

Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first scoping review to systematically map the use of open versus closed Large Language Models (LLMs) specifically within rheumatology research. Our analysis of 63 original research articles published between November 2022 and January 2026 reveals a significant reliance on proprietary systems. Most studies ($n = 50/63$; 79.37%) relied exclusively on closed-source models, with OpenAI’s GPT family dominating the landscape ($n = 55/63$; 87.30%). Conversely, the adoption of open-weight models is low, with only 4 studies (6.35%) utilizing them exclusively and 9 (14.29%) employing a hybrid approach.

The predominant reliance on closed models introduces a fundamental risk to the scientific integrity of rheumatology research: the "black box" problem. Proprietary models are subject to continuous, often silent, updates. Open models facilitate local deployment, which is crucial for data privacy when processing sensitive data. The hesitancy to adopt these models likely stems from the technical barrier of entry, requiring local GPU infrastructure, compared to the ease of use of chatbots like ChatGPT.

Regarding the version reporting, nearly half of studies did not report the date of output generation, making it impossible to map findings to a specific model iteration. Regarding the access mode, less than one third explicitly reported their access mode. Web interface versions often feature different settings (e.g., context size, temperature settings) than their API counterparts, further complicating replication.

Some studies reported using commercial AI assistants/search platforms, such as Perplexity, Bing, Copilot, OpenEvidence, or Prof VALMED. These tools typically function as front-end applications that may route queries through one or more underlying foundation models and often add retrieval/search, citations, and other orchestration layers. As a result, the specific model(s) used, the model version, and key inference settings are frequently not transparent, and outputs may vary over time as providers update back-end components.

Similarly, tools reported only as Copilot are difficult to reproduce because Copilot is a service layer that may route requests across multiple underlying models and continuously updated deployments, making the exact model/version used unclear.

The heavy reliance on paid, closed-source US-based models (OpenAI, Anthropic, Google) raises questions about long-term equity and access. Vendor lock-in and pricing changes could disproportionately affect researchers in lower-resource settings. Open models provide a pathway to "technological sovereignty," allowing diverse research groups to build and maintain their own tools without dependency on external commercial entities

A key insight emerging from our results is the need to distinguish reproducibility from transparency. In practice, these concepts are often mixed: reporting the name of a model or the general approach used may create an impression of transparency without ensuring that results can be independently reproduced. In the context of LLMs, reproducibility requires access to stable model versions, well-defined inference parameters, and sufficient methodological detail to allow re-execution under comparable conditions. Studies relying on closed, dynamically updated models may therefore be transparent in form while remaining irreproducible in substance, limiting independent verification and critical appraisal. Without reproducibility, LLM-based research risks generating isolated demonstrations rather than a coherent, accumulating body of evidence.

Reliance on proprietary LLMs also raises a form of vendor lock-in. When critical components of an analytical workflow are controlled by commercial providers, researchers have limited ability to interrogate, contest, or modify the underlying tool, which can constrain methodological choices and narrow the range of questions that can be credibly addressed. Over time, this dependency risks shifting epistemic authority from the scientific community toward external entities that govern access and model behavior.

In this context, the value of open or open-weight LLMs lies in their capacity to enable standard scientific practices. Open models permit explicit versioning, local execution, controlled experimentation, and independent auditing of analytical pipelines. These features make it possible to replicate results, assess robustness, and perform fair comparisons across studies. Framed in this way, openness is not an ideological stance but a methodological condition that facilitates reproducible and verifiable research involving complex computational systems.

Incomplete reporting in LLM-based clinical research has ethical consequences: findings that cannot be independently scrutinized may still consume resources, influence subsequent work, and shape clinical expectations despite an uncertain evidentiary basis. If current practices persist, a growing segment of the biomedical literature may become irreproducible by design, as reliance on opaque and evolving models can prevent re-examination and cumulative comparison even in well-conducted studies. Early mitigation through clearer standards and prioritization of reproducible approaches is therefore warranted.

Despite these limitations, the widespread uptake of proprietary LLMs is understandable in clinical research, largely because they offer immediate usability and feasibility for clinician-led teams. For many rheumatologists, it is realistically possible to design and execute a study using a hosted model through a familiar interface, whereas implementing and maintaining an open-access model typically requires dedicated data-science support, suitable computing infrastructure, and expertise in deployment, versioning, and security. This gap highlights a structural need to embed data scientists within clinical research groups, while simultaneously investing in targeted training so that clinicians can use open-access models responsibly. In parallel, accessible institutional platforms, providing vetted models, standardized pipelines, and governance for secure inference, could lower the technical barrier and make reproducible alternatives more attainable in routine rheumatology research

Our checklist

The checklist proposed in this study is intended to complement existing guidelines by offering a concise, domain-specific tool explicitly centered on reproducibility and transparency. By distinguishing between open and closed models, identifying non-reproducible components, and encouraging standardized reporting practices, this checklist aims to lower the barrier to reproducible LLM-based research in rheumatology.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. This review was limited to studies indexed in PubMed/MEDLINE and to English-language publications, which may have excluded relevant work. Second, we relied on an LLM-assisted extraction workflow (verified by humans), which, while efficient, carries a small risk of oversight, though we mitigated this through dual independent verification. Finally, regarding our proposed reporting checklist (Table 3), we acknowledge that this list has not undergone a Delphi consensus process. It represents the authors' synthesis of current best practices and identified gaps rather than a formally validated community standard. Nevertheless, we believe our findings provide a timely overview of current practices and highlight structural challenges that warrant immediate attention.

Conclusion

The overwhelming reliance on closed-source LLMs in rheumatology, coupled with a lack of concrete reporting directives, places the reproducibility of current research at risk. Our findings do not argue against the use of proprietary models per se, but rather highlight the urgent need for a cultural and methodological shift toward greater openness. To ensure that AI-assisted rheumatology evolves into a rigorous scientific discipline rather than a collection of snapshots of transient model versions, the research community must pivot toward transparency. This requires accelerating the adoption of viable open-source alternatives and, at a minimum, enforcing rigorous reporting standards for closed systems. Without such efforts, the transformative promise of LLMs risks amplifying, rather than resolving, the reproducibility challenges facing modern biomedical science.

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Conflict of interest statement:

DB has received payment honoraria for lectures, presentations, speakers bureaus, or support for meeting attendance from AbbVie, Galapagos, Janssen, UCB, Pfizer, Novartis, support for attending meetings from UCB, Novartis and AbbVie. He works part-time as Advisor at Savana Research, company on AI in medicine. CPR has received payment honoraria for lectures, presentations, speakers bureaus, or support for meeting attendance from AbbVie, Lilly, UCB, Biogen, Johnson & Johnson, support for attending meetings from UCB. AMG works at Roche as data scientist.

Data availability statement:

The code, prompts, and the dataset generated for the results table are provided in the Supplementary Material. The full texts of the scientific articles from which information was extracted are not shared due to copyright restrictions and legal considerations.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18664584>

Ethics statement:

This study did not require ethics approval, as it did not involve patient data, or any information governed by the GDPR.

Generative AI statement:

ChatGPT 5.2 (OpenAI), user interface (<https://chatgpt.com/>), was used to support language editing (grammar and clarity) and to assist with information extraction, API (model “gpt-5.2”), as described in the main manuscript. All AI-assisted outputs were reviewed and verified by the authors

CRedit author statement:

Alfredo Madrid García: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization.

Beatriz Merino Barbancho: Writing – original draft, Software, Visualization.

Dalifer Freites Núñez: Methodology, Validation, Data Curation Writing – review & editing.

Diego Benavent: Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

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Tables

Table 1: Minimum recommended reporting items for LLM-based rheumatology research

Domain	Item
Model identification	Full model name including variant (e.g., ChatGPT 5.2 thinking, Claude Sonnet 4.5) and reasoning effort (e.g., fast, reasoning, pro, light, standard, extended, heavy, auto, instant, thinking)
	Model type (e.g., fully open-source/open-weight/ closed-source)
	Model provider and link to the model/repository
	Exact model version and date of access/output generation
Access and execution	Mode of access (e.g., API/programmatic, web interface, local deployment)
	Known model updates during the study period
	Relevant usage restrictions or licensing terms
Reproducibility and transparency	Explicit description of reproducibility limitations
	Identification of non-reproducible components
Closed-source models (if applicable)	Justification for using a closed model
	Measures to mitigate limited transparency
	Statement on vendor lock-in
Open-source models (if applicable)	Model architecture and checkpoint
	Training data sources (if available)
	Fine-tuning procedures
	Computational resources required

Figures

Figure 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria diagram.

Figure 2: Results summary. (A) Distribution of article types, showing a predominance of original articles (84.1%). (B) Top 5 countries of first-author affiliations, led by China, Turkey, and the USA. (C) Most frequently investigated rheumatology domains. (D) Classification of study settings, primarily divided between research and education contexts. (E) Reliance on closed versus open models, highlighting that 79.4% of studies relied exclusively on closed-source systems. (F) Frequency of open-weight model families (among studies using open models), with DeepSeek and Llama being the most utilized. (G) Proportion of studies that explicitly mentioned the distinction between open and closed models (12.7%). (H) Reporting and transparency gap analysis, showing the percentage of studies reporting key reproducibility details such as prompts (76.2%), output generation dates (52.4%), access modes (30.2%), and code availability (6.3%).

Supplementary Material

The accompanying materials for this publication are provided below.

- **Supplementary material “SM_supplementary_text.docx”:** Additional text accompanying the main manuscript.
- **Supplementary spreadsheet “SM_exclusion_criteria.xlsx”:** List of the 185 articles reviewed, including each reviewer’s exclusion decisions and criteria.
- **Supplementary spreadsheet “SM_results_table.xlsx”:** Study-level variables extracted from each included study.
- **Supplementary material “SM_code.zip”:** Scripts for querying PubMed, for extracting key information from the reviewed articles, for conducting the statistical analyses and for visualization.